

Demystifying the art of isotope-enabled hydrological and climate modelling

Christian Birkel^{a,b,*}, Jodie Miller^c, Andrew Watson^d, Duc Anh Trinh^e,
Ana Maria Durán-Quesada^b, Ricardo Sánchez-Murillo^f, Chris Soulsby^{g,a},
Stefan Terzer-Wassmuth^c, Dörthe Tetzlaff^{a,h,g}, Stefan Uhlenbrookⁱ, Yuliya Vystavna^c,
Kei Yoshimura^j

^a Leibniz Institute for Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries Berlin, Germany

^b University of Costa Rica, Costa Rica

^c International Atomic Energy Agency, Austria

^d Stellenbosch University South Africa, South Africa

^e Vietnam Atomic Energy Institute, Viet Nam

^f University of Texas, Arlington, USA

^g University of Aberdeen, Scotland

^h Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany

ⁱ World Meteorological Organization, Switzerland

^j University of Tokyo, Japan

HIGHLIGHTS

- Stable water isotopes are well known tracers of the global hydrological cycle.
- SWIs derived climate science not included in influential climate reports.
- Isotope-enabled climate and hydrology modelling reduced prediction uncertainty.
- Isotope-enabled modelling can improve climate change predictions and evidence.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Over the last 20 years, we have dramatically improved hydrometeorological data including isotopes, but are we making the most of this data? Stable isotopes of oxygen and hydrogen in the water molecule (stable water isotopes – SWI) are well known tracers of the global hydrological cycle producing critical climate science. Despite this, stable water isotopes are not explicitly included in influential climate reports (e.g. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, IPCC) except for paleoclimate reconstructions. Continuous developments in modelling approaches have now made isotope-enabled modelling of climate and hydrology more powerful and easier to perform, reducing prediction uncertainty and providing more robust simulations. We argue that it is time to

* Corresponding author at: Leibniz Institute for Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, Berlin, Germany.

E-mail address: christian.birkel@ucr.ac.cr (C. Birkel).

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incorporate stable water isotopes and isotope-enabled modelling into mainstream hydroclimatic forecasting with the prospect of vastly improving climate change predictions and evidence.

1. Climate prediction versus reality: are we getting anywhere?

Our understanding of climate change and how it is evolving, is based on models that take data from diverse sources to project what would happen in the future given certain known constraints, e.g. increasing CO₂ and temperature in the atmosphere (Douville et al., 2021). These models shape our thinking on the global commitments that are needed to mitigate climate change, the societal and economic compromises we need to adapt to climate change, and the financial and government willpower to do both (McLaren and Markusson, 2020). Whilst it is undeniable that the climate is changing at unprecedented rates, there is considerable debate about whether historical models have accurately predicted the climate conditions we now find ourselves affected by (Hausfather, 2020). This is particularly relevant when it comes to understanding long-term changes in the hydrological cycle for which observations can be biased and physical and chemical processes are not fully understood.

This debate partly relates to changes in the climate model constructs that are now pivoting back to scenarios with emissions included and more recently the socio-economic pathways framework (Gidden et al., 2019). These variations in model constructs are driven by attempts to improve the matching of the model predictions with observed climate change (Broecker, 2017). One of the most profound impacts of climate change is the global increase in air temperatures that has brought about more frequent extreme weather in most parts of the planet. Climate models assumed that the Clausius-Clapeyron relation, which says that atmospheric precipitable water scales with the water vapor content of

saturation that is temperature depend, would hold under changing climate conditions. However, analysis of precipitation extremes and associated temperature change found that this assumption was not always valid (Fowler et al., 2021), contributing to ongoing uncertainty in modelled predictions about the nature and scale of climate change and its impact.

But is there another way to better evaluate model forecasts and predict climate change impacts? We think so. Understanding shifts in the hydrological cycle requires knowledge of the transfer and feedback processes between energy and moisture in the hydrosphere, biosphere and atmosphere. SWIs are excellent natural tracers of these processes that are not altered by chemical reactions (e.g. Dee et al., 2023) but were limited by analytical constraints (expensive mass spectrometry and stable O and H isotopes not collected simultaneously). From 2007, the development of laser absorption spectrometry (LAS), meant that higher sample throughput could be achieved, with simultaneous analysis of stable O and H isotopes, at a fraction of previous costs (Lis et al., 2008). This development dramatically increased the availability of higher temporal and spatial resolution SWI data sets for water in different components of the hydrological cycle (Fig. 1) (e.g. Terzer-Wassmuth et al., 2021). In spite of this, policy-relevant climate change information has not incorporated SWI data (Douville et al., 2021).

2. Isotope data availability: a critical pressure point in addressing climate change

Despite the demonstrable advantage of maintaining observation

Fig. 1. Normalized pre- and post LAS advent (~2007) publication metrics of “isotope-enabled” and more general “tracer-aided model” SCOPUS search words (climate and hydrology total since 1980: 733) compared to the global average land surface temperature anomaly (in red). All other published “model” papers in grey (total since 1980: 75511) and model publications concerned with “uncertainty” and with “climate change adaptation” show the overall increasing trend, although lagging the overall number of “model” publications with adaptation only starting in the early 2000s. Despite unquantified relationships, clear positive trends among all variables warrant a detailed future analysis of interactions and cross-relationships.

networks and their importance to revealing changes in earth system processes and ground-truthing model and remote sensing products, monitoring networks are declining worldwide due to economic constraints (Wohl et al., 2012). This limits observational data, generating large uncertainties in projections which are nevertheless used to devise climate adaptation strategies. It is here that isotope-enabled model projections can bridge the significant gap between academic small-scale models, which are often data-rich, and larger-scale, data-scarce modelling used in national water management decisions.

The incorporation of SWIs into modelling frameworks requires data sets that have sufficient longevity at the required resolution in both time and space. The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) GNIP (Global Network of Isotopes in Precipitation) and GNIR (Global Network of Isotopes in Rivers) databases of monthly precipitation and surface water isotope data have facilitated robust water balance assessments at annual and monthly scales (IAEA TECDOC, 2022). To generate more detailed simulations within the hydrosphere, requires daily or sub-daily precipitation isotope data. However, collecting high-frequency precipitation data is challenging. Climate change has fundamentally altered precipitation patterns in many regions increasing spatial and temporal complexity requiring additional observation data than what has been collected previously. In particular, the increasing incidence of extreme precipitation events on short time frames (sub-daily), is difficult to capture accurately in manual sampling campaigns (Sánchez-Murillo et al., 2019).

An alternative option to generate the required precipitation input data, is simulated precipitation isotope data at different temporal scales from isotope-enabled climate models (e.g. Bong et al., 2024). These models have the advantage of tracking moisture transport but also identifying where, and more importantly, how precipitation is generated using the isotopes to quantify fractionation during condensation, and thus quantifying moisture exchange at various spatial and temporal scales. This is a critical step forward in the science of isotope-enabled modelling because SWI data supports more robust simulations of hydrometeorological variables due to the evaluation of an additional quasi-independent variable - the water source isotope composition. Through this isotope-enabled climate models have increasingly improved precipitation and even temperature forecasts (Tada et al., 2021). The inherent variability in precipitation though, means that there are translation problems between global precipitation patterns and catchment-scale precipitation data because of the relative contribution of surface feedback processes that are not represented at the large scale but become more relevant for smaller spatial scales. Whilst simulated precipitation data must still be bias-corrected before incorporation in isotope-enabled hydrological modelling (Watson et al., 2024), the gap between simulated and observed data is decreasing continuously gaining critical information on water cycles and budgets at reduced uncertainty.

3. A messy art? Rethinking the accessibility of isotope-enabled modelling

Having the data necessary to do isotope-enabled modelling and applying isotope-enabled models are not the same thing, as many a frustrated modeler will know. For isotope-enabled modelling, the need to understand modelling and coding frameworks, potential disparate model calibration results, as well as isotope hydrology, and to have the right datasets, put these novel approaches outside the reach of those but a select few. It is only in the last ~5 years that isotope-enabled models have become available to both scientists and water managers through the development of “plug and play” models accessible through a graphical user interface (e.g. the Jena Adaptable Modelling System JAMS/J2000-iso: 15). This development has driven further demand for this type of modelling, accelerating steps to make more isotope-enabled models accessible to non-specialists. The availability of isotope precipitation data from isotope-enabled climate models has opened up

accessibility of isotope-enabled hydrological models for regions with sparse measured isotope data. Ongoing progress in isotope modelling includes the transition of isotope-enabled regional climate models from a historical use in paleoclimate reconstruction to advanced understanding of severe weather. Despite progress, uptake of such model output is mostly limited to the isotope-modelling community!

4. Adapting to the future: bringing isotopes into the mainstream

The uptake of outputs from isotope-enabled modelling by policy and decision makers for climate adaptation is an essential step for strengthening water management and progress towards achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals since isotopes as an integrative tracer can be used to compare diverse hydroclimatic systems across time and space. Increased uptake of isotope-enabled simulations can be enhanced by strengthening cross-organizational collaboration between the IAEA and e.g., the World Meteorological Organization as well as global research groups promoting novel and alternative sampling and model evaluation strategies towards a higher spatial coverage. Such data can be used to spatially and temporally train and evaluate isotope-enabled hydrology and climate models further increasing robustness. Professional outreach strategies are required to better communicate the benefits of isotope-enabled modelling and promote the wider integration of SWIs in Earth System Models. Further, open access and user-friendly isotope-enabled model codes with associated training activities, will build a community of critical-mass required for mainstreaming these models. We are promoting these activities in the hope that this will encourage the IPCC and climate change community to include isotope and isotope-enabled model studies in their assessments and recommendations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Christian Birkel: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Jodie Miller:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Andrew Watson:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Duc Anh Trinh:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Ana Maria Durán-Quesada:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Ricardo Sánchez-Murillo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Chris Soulsby:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Stefan Terzer-Wassmuth:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Dörthe Tetzlaff:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Stefan Uhlenbrook:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Yuliya Vystavna:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Kei Yoshimura:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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